

Challenges and perspectives of neurodivergent professionals in the job market

Desafios e perspectivas dos profissionais neurodivergentes no mercado de trabalho

Desafíos y perspectivas de los profesionales neurodivergentes en el entorno laboral

Recebido
Received
Recibido
Dez. 2024

Aceito
Accepted
Aceptado
Mar. 2025

Publicado
Published
Publicado
Jul./Set. 2025
Jul./Sep. 2025

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e-ISSN
2965-3339

DOI
10.29327/2385846.3.4-8

São Paulo
v. 3 | n. 4
v. 3 | i. 4
e34206
Julho-Setembro
July-September
Julio-Septiembre
2025

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Abstract:

This study analyzes the barriers faced by neurodivergent individuals when entering the job market, considering Neurodevelopmental Disorders (ASD and ADHD) and Learning Disabilities (Dyslexia). Through descriptive qualitative research that combined a literature review and structured questionnaires, the lack of adaptation in selection processes and the lack of support in the corporate environment stand out as the main challenges for the inclusion of neurodivergent professionals. The results show that 21% of these professionals report difficulties in finding employment precisely because of the lack of adaptation in the processes. In addition to identifying these barriers, the study presents inclusion practices adopted by some companies and the benefits that neurocognitive diversity offers, such as greater employee engagement and innovation. The research also points out that the lack of knowledge about neurodivergence is a widespread problem in society, making it difficult to create inclusive policies. By advocating for changes in companies, the article reinforces the importance of creating more inclusive work environments that recognize and value different talents.

Keywords: *Neurodivergence; Job market; Inclusion; Challenges.*

Resumo:

Este estudo analisa as barreiras que pessoas neurodivergentes enfrentam ao inserir-se no mercado de trabalho, considerando Transtornos do Neurodesenvolvimento (TEA e TDAH) e Transtornos de Aprendizagem (Dislexia). Por meio de uma pesquisa qualitativa descritiva que combinou revisão de literatura e questionários estruturados, destaca-se a falta de adaptação nos processos seletivos e a carência de suporte no ambiente corporativo como os principais desafios para a inserção de profissionais neurodivergentes. Os resultados mostram que 21% desses profissionais relatam dificuldades em conseguir emprego justamente pela falta de adaptação nos processos. Além de identificar essas barreiras, o estudo apresenta práticas de inclusão adotadas por algumas empresas e os benefícios que a diversidade neurocognitiva oferece, como maior engajamento dos colaboradores e inovação. A

pesquisa também aponta que o desconhecimento sobre a neurodivergência é um problema generalizado na sociedade, dificultando a criação de políticas inclusivas. Ao defender mudanças nas empresas, o artigo reforça a importância de criar ambientes de trabalho mais inclusivos que reconheçam e valorizem diferentes talentos.

Palavras-chave: Neurodivergência; Mercado de trabalho; Inclusão; Desafios.

Resumen:

Este estudio analiza las barreras que enfrentan las personas neurodivergentes al insertarse en el mercado laboral, considerando los Trastornos del Neurodesarrollo (TEA y TDAH) y los Trastornos del Aprendizaje (Dislexia). A través de una investigación cualitativa descriptiva que combinó una revisión de la literatura y cuestionarios estructurados, la falta de adaptación en los procesos de selección y la carencia de apoyo en el entorno corporativo se destacan como los principales desafíos para la inserción de profesionales neurodivergentes. Los resultados muestran que el 21% de estos profesionales reportan dificultades para conseguir empleo justamente por la falta de adaptación en los procesos. Además de identificar estas barreras, el estudio presenta prácticas de inclusión adoptadas por algunas empresas y los beneficios que la diversidad neurocognitiva ofrece, como un mayor compromiso de los colaboradores e innovación. La investigación también señala que el desconocimiento sobre la neurodiversidad es un problema generalizado en la sociedad, dificultando la creación de políticas inclusivas. Al abogar por cambios en las empresas, el artículo refuerza la importancia de crear entornos de trabajo más inclusivos que reconozcan y valoren los diferentes talentos.

Palabras clave: Neurodivergencia; Entorno laboral; Inclusión; Desafíos.

1. INTRODUCTION

Discussions about neurodivergence and the job market have gained visibility in the corporate and academic sectors in recent years. Neurodivergence refers to an atypical neurological configuration that influences how people process, learn, and socialize; these differences culminate in unique skills and creative, innovative thinking. Companies worldwide have adapted their human resources processes and work environments to meet the needs of neurodivergent professionals. However, there are still challenges to overcome to ensure they have full access to the same opportunities and working conditions as others, given that estimates indicate that approximately 80% of neurodivergent people are unemployed or underemployed (Austin and Pisano, 2017; Pinho, 2024). Furthermore, the theory points out that it is not the abilities of neurodivergent people (NDPs) that prevent them from working professionally, but rather the way organizations conduct their selection processes (Krzeminska et al., 2019). Thence, disseminating information on this topic is fundamental to promoting diversity and inclusion, reducing stigma, and raising societal awareness. Moreover, the scientific literature on this subject is predominantly focused on the organizational perspective; accordingly, this article aims to fill this gap by recognizing the importance of individuals' voices and offering an in-depth view of their professional experiences. Thus, the guiding question is: "What challenges do neurodivergent people face in the process of entering the job market, and what are their perceptions regarding the inclusion practices adopted by companies?" Understanding the realities of these professionals can help make this marginalized group more visible and promote inclusive actions.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This topic will address the concepts of neurodivergence and its crucial manifestations – Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, Autism Spectrum Disorder, Tourette Syndrome, and Dyslexia. When intersected with the job market, multiple challenges faced by neurodivergent professionals are observed, highlighting the need for corporations to adopt inclusive practices to attract and retain these talents.

2.1 Conceptualization of neurodivergence and its main variations

Neuroatypicality or neurodivergence – a term coined by Kassiane Asasumasu in the 2000s – is a class of human neurodiversity characterized by natural variations in brain function, in which people process information and interact socially in ways that differ from the "typical" pattern, leading to unique abilities and innovative ways of thinking. As Singer (2017) claims, if neuroatypicality is classified as a medical condition, it should be treated the same way; therefore, it should not be considered a disorder or disease that requires a cure. This approach challenges standards of normality, promoting the inclusion and acceptance of people with different cognitive styles, intending to make social and work structures more flexible, accommodating their needs and talents, instead

of trying to adapt them to the system (Costa et al., 2016; Krzeminska et al., 2019; Viana and Manrique, 2023). Neurodivergence encompasses numerous variations, such as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), Learning Disabilities, Dyslexia, Dyspraxia, Dyscalculia, Behavioral Disabilities, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD), Tourette Syndrome, Social Anxiety Disorder, and gifted or highly skilled individuals, among other conditions (Basto, 2021).

As maintained by the Ministry of Health, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) can vary from person to person and manifest itself in different ways in children, adolescents, and adults. Despite this, it is classified into three essential categories: inattention, hyperactivity, and impulsiveness (WHO, 2021). Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD), the official name since 2014, is a health condition that can be characterized by deficits in social communication – verbal and non-verbal communication – and behavioral characteristics – restricted interests and repetitive movements. According to Klim apud Barbosa (2014), it is defined as "a family of conditions marked by the early onset of delays and deviations in the development of social, communicative, and other skills (our translation)."

Besides, Gilles de la Tourette Syndrome (TS) is a neuropsychiatric pathology characterized by multiple motor tics and one or more vocal tics. Symptoms typically onset between 6 and 7 years of age but can be observed up to 18 years of age. Most movements resemble intentional acts but, in reality, are impulsive and are usually accompanied by sounds such as grunts, barks, word utterances, and even swear words (Vicente, Tavares and Siqueira, 2023). TS is frequently accompanied by a variety of behavioral comorbidities, such as Obsessive-Compulsive Disorder (OCD) or ADHD; the tics and behavioral disorders can lead to significant impairment in family and social interactions, school and professional performance, and often seriously impact the quality of life of patients (Billnitzer and Jankovic, 2020). Regarding dyslexia, it is a neurodevelopmental disorder that affects basic reading, writing, and spelling skills, that is, forms of language. It is considered a specific learning disorder because its symptoms generally affect the academic performance of students, without any other alteration (neurological, sensory, or motor) justifying the observed difficulties (Instituto ABCD, 2021).

2.2 Intersection between neurodivergence and the labor market

Among the world's population, it is estimated that 10% to 20% have atypical brain function (Galindo, 2024). In Brazil, for instance, approximately 4% of the population has dyslexia (Brazil, 2024), and 5.2% of adults have ADHD (Brazil, 2022). In the United States, on average, 0.13% of people have Tourette's syndrome (Tinker et al., 2022), and data from the CDC (2023) indicate that the prevalence of people with ASD increased from 0.7% to 2.8% in 20 years. As can be observed, people with disabilities comprise a significant portion of society and require professional opportunities in accordance with their aptitudes. The progress achieved by the neurodivergent community in the last decade has considerably boosted awareness in society and organizations, as large technology companies in various countries have begun to recognize the advantages of hiring

people with neurodivergence (PNDs), leading to greater team engagement and better results; in fact, an Australian company found that the productivity of PNDs was 30% higher than that of neurotypical people (Austin and Pisano, 2017; Chammas and Hernandez, 2022).

Although many companies promote diversity and inclusion among their workforce, many still face difficulties in adapting. Resistance to change can stem from both organizational cultures, with pre-existing values and norms, and from a lack of preparedness to implement better structures and processes (Blackburn, 2023). As stated by Basto (2021), the key challenges in the inclusion process are organizational culture, manager engagement, individualized attention, and highlighting potential. Despite these adversities, companies are adopting a more inclusive, sensitive approach to address neurodiversity within their organizations. Communication around this topic generally aims to raise awareness of cognitive diversity and promote inclusion through educational campaigns, training, and awareness-raising initiatives. Companies are recognizing that such actions can bring advantages such as greater creativity, innovation, and the resolution of complex problems (LeFevre-Levy et al., 2023).

Blackburn (2023) highlights several positive characteristics of each neurodivergence, such as the exceptional attention to detail and motivation of people with ADHD, the skillful attention and memory of individuals with ASD, and the reliability of visual information in those with dyslexia. In this sense, enterprises should adopt internal inclusion practices and policies that reform selection processes to attract and retain these talents, adapt positions and responsibilities, and provide training for other employees. Furthermore, awareness campaigns combined with corporate programs will enable the proper integration of these employees into the team while meeting their needs (Pinho, 2024).

As claimed by Rodrigues et al. (p. 16, 2024, our translation), “companies that incorporate inclusive practices appropriately can benefit by becoming a strategic organization, with more innovation and authenticity, as they will have diverse perspectives for decision-making,” in addition to commitment, talent retention, respect for differences, a sense of belonging, and appreciation of all people. Moreover, Federal Law No. 12.764/12 ensures people with ASD access to the job market. Nevertheless, this is progress, it is necessary to develop public policies that permit the professional empowerment of all neurodivergent people. For Souza, Tavares, and Mota (2024), current legislation excellently fulfills the protective role for this population; however, the obstacle to inclusion, in any context, is due to the search for information and support by society itself, and therefore, it is fundamental to reduce stigma via awareness-raising actions that promote the empowerment of people with disabilities.

3. METHOD

This study uses a descriptive qualitative research approach, combining literature review and questionnaires, to describe the challenges of neurodivergence in the corporate world (Denzin and Lincoln, 2006). The methodology was chosen

because it offers a broad view of the topic, integrating theoretical analysis with the collection of participants' perceptions (Creswell, 2007). The initial literature review provided an understanding of the topic's complexity and challenges, offered a theoretical basis for the impact of neurodivergence on society and companies, and highlighted the importance of inclusive practices.

Data collection was conducted using a structured questionnaire containing 8 (eight) open-ended questions, made available digitally between October 16 and 30, 2024, via platforms such as WhatsApp, LinkedIn, and bulletin boards, chosen for their accessibility and ability to reach a diverse audience. Participants included neurodivergent individuals and professionals from companies with inclusive practices. Data analysis was conducted using content analysis techniques, identifying patterns and categories related to the impact of neurodivergence in the workplace. The interviews were transcribed and reviewed to ensure the accuracy of the information and to guarantee compliance with the LGPD – General Data Protection Law.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This article aims to understand the individual experiences of the neurodivergent participants; that is, it will not generalize to the entire population. To this end, data triangulation was used, comparing results from the literature with the responses of the 31 participants to identify convergences and divergences.

In accordance with Pinho (2024), occasionally PNDs may present high abilities or giftedness, differentiating them from intellectual disability, in which the cognitive and behavioral level is lower than expected for their developmental stage. Nonetheless, the terms remain associated, indicating the need for clarification, as shown in Figure 1.

Within this group, the prevalence of individuals with ADHD was identified (Figure 1), aged between 21 and 25 years (Figure 2), and approximately 52% were students or graduates of higher education (Figure 3). Furthermore, 21% of these individuals are currently employed (Figure 4), primarily in administrative and operational roles (Figure 5).

Figure 1 – Types of neurodivergence among participants

Source: authors (2024)

Figure 2 – Age range of participants

Source: authors (2024)

Figure 3 – Educational level of the participants

Source: authors (2024)

Figure 4 – Are you currently working?

Source: authors (2024)

Figure 5 – If you are working, what is your area and position?

Source: authors (2024)

Next, Figure 6 presents the challenges neurodivergent professionals face when entering the job market. Of these, 33% highlight the difficulty in conveying their skills and experiences, and 21% point out the lack of adaptation in selection processes. This finding aligns with the literature, as can be seen in some of the responses: “[...] I need to read the text several times to absorb what was asked, and I end up not finishing some of it. Additionally, in interviews, trying to act 'normally' drains a lot of my energy and obviously did not yield results”; “[...] very long selection processes, where I ended up getting lost in the stages [...]” and “Difficulty in showing my skills in tests, since some were not clear to me”. For Krzeminska et al. (2019, our translation), conventional processes tend to limit the talents of neurodivergent people; hence, adapting the job market is urgent.

Table 1 presents the perceptions of 32.3% of participants who noticed some type of difference in treatment during selection processes. The lack of patience from recruiters and negative responses corroborate Blackburn's (2023) findings regarding companies' unpreparedness to deal with people with neurodivergence, underscoring the importance of training and adapting processes. In contrast, one participant stated that not perceiving such a difference “[...] might even be a bad thing since they haven't adapted to people with neurodivergence (our translation)” meaning there hasn't been a sufficiently assertive adaptation to meet the needs of people with neurodivergence and make them feel comfortable disclosing their disorders.

As Blackburn (2023) stated, implementing inclusion programs is essential for both professionals and companies to reap the benefits of a neurodiverse culture. Nevertheless, 84% of those surveyed had never participated in inclusion initiatives (Figure 7), revealing a lack of internal policies within organizations aimed at this population and the need to raise awareness among those responsible for their development, as they will be responsible for identifying and implementing best practices.

Figure 6 –In your experience, which of the following factors do you consider the biggest challenge in the job search?

Source: authors (2024)

Table 1 – Was there a difference in the treatment received in selection processes compared to other candidates?

Classes	Items
Yes 32,3%	<p>A: Yes, I have noticed impatient or dismissive looks towards me in some interviews.</p> <p>A: I realized that recruiters often lack patience when I need more time to understand a question.</p> <p>A: I felt I was judged too quickly because of my difficulty paying attention.</p>
No 67,7%	<p>A: No, because I've never dared to say that I have ADHD.</p> <p>A: No, because it can camouflage neurodivergence.</p> <p>A: Not directly, but I felt they demanded quick and direct answers.</p>

Source: authors (2024)

It is worth noting that the 16% of people with disabilities who have already participated in some inclusive action (Table 2) positively evaluated the experience, but highlighted aspects that could have been improved, such as "there is a lack of specific support for people with dyslexia" and "there is a lack of greater understanding of our individualities." For Basto (2021), individualized attention remains a barrier to overcome and, thus, adaptation to each neurodivergence is fundamental not only in selection processes but also in work environments.

Figure 7 –Have you ever participated in any inclusion programs or initiatives for neurodivergent

Source: authors (2024)

Table 2 – Which inclusion programs or initiatives have you participated in?

Number of participants	Description of the initiatives
1	Supported Employment Program
1	Inclusion and awareness campaign
3	Participants do not specify inclusion programs.

Source: authors (2024)

Participants also highlighted the most significant difficulties in integrating into the work environment. In Table 3, three categories stood out in the analysis of the responses: internal processes, interpersonal relationships, and attention deficit. In agreement with Pinho (2024), we found it essential to develop corporate policies for neurodivergent employees, provide training for others, respect individual learning paces, adapt bureaucratic processes to facilitate understanding for everyone, and monitor the integration of people with disabilities into the team, thereby making interpersonal interactions more harmonious.

Moreover, to address these obstacles, neurodivergent professionals believe that companies could offer support through various means, such as adapting workspaces, making processes with a significant sensory impact more flexible, and encouraging awareness, especially among leadership. This last point is supported by Romanov (2024), who states that senior management and managers should be the first to participate in neurodivergence training. Finally, and considered fundamental by most participants, it is essential to provide psychological support within institutions, readily available and prepared to assist in both occupational and personal situations (Table 4).

Table 3 – When starting a new job, what were the most significant difficulties you faced in adapting to the work environment?

Classes	Items
Internal processes	<p>A: To keep up with the expected pace of work.</p> <p>A: Difficulty with rules [...] I felt very exhausted trying to read</p> <p>A: [...] Poor onboarding</p> <p>A: Understanding the requirements without a straightforward step-by-step process was quite challenging.</p> <p>A: [...] I need to review everything a trillion times at the beginning, until I get the hang of it.</p>
Interpersonal relationships	<p>A: [...]the feeling of being alone and different/excluded bothered me</p> <p>A: Interacting with new people [...]</p> <p>A: The lack of preparedness of some people in the environment.</p> <p>A: If [...] I stayed quiet, organizing things in my head or doing more introverted activities, but I would already become a laughingstock.</p> <p>A: If [...] someone comes to interrupt me [...] it ends up distracting me and leaving me frustrated [...]</p>
Attention deficit	<p>A: Too much information</p> <p>A: Focus on one task at a time and maintain seriousness.</p> <p>A: I need to constantly remind myself of things [...] this is terrible because I often can't do it.</p>

Source: authors (2024)

Table 4 – Could companies offer any kind of support or adaptation to facilitate your work?

Classes	Items
Adaptation of processes	<p>A: [...] other methods that don't rely so heavily on writing, such as images and cartoons</p> <p>A: [...] well-specified tasks [...] remote work options to avoid sensory problems [...] I can't have noise when I'm preparing to speak in public or doing a task that requires a lot of focus.</p> <p>A: Yes, I think visual instruction methods and direct feedback would help.</p> <p>A: [...] it should be allowed to use either noise-canceling headphones or headphones with music at a low volume, [...] be more flexible in terms of doing tasks, often [...] we find an easier and more practical way for ourselves, but it's considered wrong because it's not the standard [...]</p>
Flexibility	<p>A: [...]Flexibility in handling specific tasks, more inclusive job openings.</p> <p>A: I think companies could ask each neurodivergent person what kind of support they need.</p> <p>A: [...] adapting to see where the neurodivergent person might fit best [...]</p>
Professional support	<p>A: [...] psychological support, at least during the first few days of work.</p> <p>A: [...] a point of support with someone to ask questions [...]</p>
Awareness	<p>A: Yes, more information and awareness about neurodivergences are needed to avoid hasty judgments.</p> <p>A: [...] an environment where the boss has more empathy [...]</p> <p>A: [...] they diminish what we feel because we don't have enough knowledge [...]</p> <p>A: [...] training for leaders to learn how to deal with us better [...]</p>

Source: authors (2024)

Based on the data presented in Figure 8, it is clear that 52% of these professionals believe that companies are not prepared to receive people with disabilities. In this regard, Souza, Tavares, and Mota (2024) emphasize that it is the responsibility of society and organizations to seek information and promote awareness campaigns. Besides, Blackburn (2023) highlights that an organizational culture that supports inclusive practices normalizes neurological variations. In this way, it is possible to create a positive environment that prioritizes reducing stigma and empowering this marginalized group.

Figure 8 – In your opinion, are companies prepared to receive and include neurodivergent professionals?

Source: authors (2024)

Additionally, Table 5 aligns with Austin and Pisano's (2017) ideas, showing that

difficulties people with ASD face in entering the job market are associated with HR processes for large-scale recruitment. In this context, the skills commonly required and evaluated are good communication, teamwork, emotional intelligence, and interpersonal relationships; when these criteria are not met, they place neurodivergent individuals at a disadvantage compared to neurotypical people, minimize their potential, and immediately exclude them, making the job search more exhausting.

In view of this, to ensure a fair selection process, specific needs and facilities inherent to all neurodivergent individuals must be considered, as well as replacing traditional interviews as selection methods with practical assessments, guaranteeing candidates the opportunity to demonstrate their unique abilities in performing tasks (Chammas and Hernandez, 2022; Pinho, 2024). It is also worth highlighting the importance of including neurodivergent individuals in the selection process, providing support to candidates and contributing to the development of new organizational practices.

Table 5 – What could companies do to create a more inclusive selection process and work environment?

Classes	Items
Processes	<p>A: [...] professionals working in the neurological field, as they will have greater expertise in helping to create these selection processes [...], instead of asking, perhaps they should see in practice the skills/competencies that neurodivergent individuals possess.</p> <p>A: Utilize neurodivergent individuals in the selection process. And have a group within the company, composed of neurodivergent and neurotypical people, to work on finding “middle ground.”</p>
Structure	<p>A: Regarding the selection process, I really don't know. Ideally, the work environment would be remote if the type of work allows it. Otherwise, offer a calm and welcoming atmosphere and headphones with excellent noise isolation.</p> <p>A: There could be a quieter rest area or room with some beanbag chairs in case of a crisis.</p>
Empathy	<p>A: More sensitivity in conversations, patience with employees with or without neurodivergence, optimism, and initiative help.</p> <p>A: To be patient during the interviews and make the process more comfortable and empathetic.</p> <p>A: To empower recruiters to understand that everyone has their own pace of learning and communication.</p>

Source: authors (2024)

5. CONCLUSION

This study, through analysis of responses to the questionnaire, provided an understanding of the experiences and challenges faced by participating neurodivergent professionals, aligned with the literature review from a corporate perspective, and successfully achieved its proposed objectives. Thus, it was identified that obstacles span all stages of entering the job market, highlighting the difficulties faced by 33% of neurodivergent individuals in demonstrating their skills, as traditional selection processes become inefficient at evaluating such competencies. Moreover, the qualitative research allowed participants to express

their perceptions of the inclusion practices adopted by organizations, highlighting deficits in awareness among teams and leaders, a lack of preparedness to address diverse needs, and unequal treatment, as reported by 32.3% of these professionals. In this sense, companies should recognize the importance of inclusion and the competitive advantage that diversity provides, considering the heterogeneity of neurodivergent individuals, to rethink their processes, adapt work environments, and offer specialized professional support.

However, we acknowledge the limitations of our study and the importance of future, more in-depth research with larger samples and methodologies that allow for a more direct dialogue with neurodivergent professionals and companies. We suggest, for example, investigating the experiences of these professionals across different sectors and hierarchical levels, including the presence of neurodivergent leaders in companies, given that only 3% of participants reported working in management, and evaluating the impact of mentoring and professional support programs.

Hence, to build a more inclusive future of work, companies, universities, governments, and civil society must unite in support of neurodiversity. This implies implementing public policies that guarantee the rights of neurodivergent individuals, training human resources professionals to deal with this diversity, and creating support networks to assist them in their professional journeys. By valuing neurodiversity, we are not only promoting inclusion but also enriching our work environments and fostering innovation. After all, each brain is unique and has much to contribute to a more just and equitable world.

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